

DEDAN KIMATHI UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING

DEPARTMENT OF MECHATRONIC ENGINEERING

FULL NAME	REG No.
MURIUKI DENNIS MUTUMA	E022-0319/2010
KANG'IRI SAMUEL MACHARIA (SirmaxforD)	E022-0307/2010

COURSE: BSc. MECHATRONIC ENGINEERING

DEVELOPMENT OF A LOW-COST SUBTRACTIVE-ADDITIVE MACHINE

SUPERVISORS:

Dr. Eng. Jean B. Byiringiro (Ph.D. Reg. Eng)

MR. Sultan M. Hamid

This project work is submitted to the department of Mechatronic Engineering in partial fulfilment for the award of Bachelor of Science degree in Mechatronic Engineering

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DECLARATION

This project work is our original work, except where due acknowledgement is made in the text, and to the best of my knowledge has not been previously submitted to Dedan Kimathi University of Technology or any other institution for the award of a degree or diploma.

NAME: MURIUKI DENNIS MUTUMA

REG. No.: E022-0319/2010

SIGNATURE:

DATE:

NAME: KANG'IRI SAMUEL MACHARIA

REG. No.: E022-0307/2010

SIGNATURE:

DATE:

SUPERVISOR CONFIRMATION

This project work has been submitted to the Department of Mechatronic Engineering, Dedan Kimathi University of Technology, with our approval as the supervisors:

- 1. Name: **Dr. Eng. Jean B. Byiringiro (Ph.D. Reg. Eng)**

Signature:

Date:

- 2. Name: **MR. Sultan M. Hamid**

Signature:

Date:

DEDICATION

To our families, lecturers, fellow classmates and friends whose continued support and encouragement were fundamental in accomplishment of our purpose and ambition.

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Firstly, blessed be the God and Father of our Lord Jesus Christ, who has blessed us.

We gratefully appreciate the following individuals for their assistance which was vital throughout the development of the SAM Machine:

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ABSTRACT

Additive manufacturing refers to the process of making a three-dimensional object from a digital file where successive layers of material are added under computer control until the entire object is created. Subtractive manufacturing on the other hand refers to the use of a machine tool to remove material from a component so as to obtain the desired size and shape. For a Numerical Control (NC) machine tool, the motion is automated.

The purpose of this project is to develop a computer numerically controlled machine that can handle both subtractive and additive tasks at a low cost. Unlike other machines in the market, which exist separately as either subtractive (CNC) or additive (3D Printer), this machine aims at combining the two at a low cost. We considered this as a useful research in areas like; improving machines in modern manufacturing and production industries, a Learning Kit for Students and also in the production of components using different materials all at once in one machine.

On carrying out a research about work done previously, we developed a software design and architecture by which our machine shall operate. We then did a power supply design. Suitable microcontroller and motor drivers were selected and their corresponding designs done; with the help of proteus software, to make a control block. A mechanical design was done in Autodesk Inventor software which assisted us to come up with a proper machine block. We planned to complete this project by the end of two semesters as shown in the work plan.

Table of Contents

DECLARATION.....	i
DEDICATION	ii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	iii
ABSTRACT	iv
Table of Figures	vii
Table of tables.....	ix
List of equations used	x
Abbreviations used.....	xi
List of softwares used.....	xii
1. INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 Problem statement	2
1.2 Objectives	3
1.2.1 Main Objective	3
1.2.2 Specific Objectives	3
1.2.3 Scope of the project.....	4
1.3 Justification	4
2.1 Introduction	5
2.2 Components of Numerical Control Machine.....	6
2.3 Control Loops.....	7
2.3.1 Open loop control	7
2.3.2 Closed loop control	8
2.4 Nomenclature for axes coordinate system	10
2.5 Types of programming and interpolation.....	11
2.6 Circular interpolation	13
3. METHODOLOGY	14
3.1 Outline.....	14
3.2 Software part.....	14
3.2.1 Machine software-program architecture	14
3.2.2 Machine software requirements	15
3.2.3 Machine software design	15

3.3 Electronics part	16
3.3.1 Machine electronics architecture	16
3.3.2 Machine electronics requirements	17
3.3.3 Machine electronics design.....	18
3.4 Mechanical part.....	23
3.4.1 Machine mechanical architecture	24
3.4.2 Machine mechanical requirements	24
3.4.3 Machine mechanical design.....	24
3.5 Overall machine operation flow chart.....	27
4. VIRTUAL IMPLEMENTATION	28
5. RESULTS.....	31
5.1 Errors and Analysis.....	37
5.2 Machine features	38
5.3 Machine caution.....	39
5.4 Skills used/needed.....	39
5.5 Troubleshoots	39
6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION	40
6.1 Challenges.....	41
BUDGET	42
WORKING SCHEDULE	43
REFERENCES.....	44
APPENDIX 1: CIRCUIT DESIGNS AND ELECTRONICS SIMULATION OUTPUTS....	45
APPENDIX 2: SAM MACHINE MECHANICAL DESIGNS	49
APPENDIX 3: SAM MACHINE GUI SOFTWARE PROGRAM.....	56
APPENDIX 4: SAM MACHINE MICROCONTROLLER PROGRAM	66

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Open loop control block diagram.	8
Figure 2: Open loop control system.	8
Figure 3: Closed loop block diagram.	9
Figure 4: Closed loop control system.	9
Figure 6: Right-hand rule.	10
Figure 7: Main axis and rotational axis coordinate system.	10
Figure 8: Point to point system.	12
Figure 9: Continuous path system.	12
Figure 10: machine software-program architecture.	14
Figure 11: Machine software design.	15
Figure 12: Machine electronics architecture.	16
Figure 13: Regulated power supply.	18
Figure 14: single-phase full-wave rectifier.	19
Figure 15: Power Supply Design.	21
Figure 16: Microcontroller interfacing design.	22
Figure 17: Motor drivers interfacing design.	22
Figure 18: Electronics design.	23
Figure 19: From control block to machine block.	24
Figure 20: Machine mechanical design assembly.	26
Figure 21: Machine block parts.	26
Figure 22: Various machine block views.	27
Figure 23: Overall machine operation.	27
Figure 29: X stepper moving clockwise 16 steps/rev.	28
Figure 30: Y stepper moving counterclockwise 16 steps/rev.	29
Figure 31: Control of stepper motor.	30
Figure 32: Designed user interface software.	31
Figure 40: Machine block wood parts and Control block parts.	31
Figure 41: Assembled machine block.	32
Figure 42: Soldering, Wiring, Labeling and Testing involved.	32
Figure 43: Machine software GUI design captured when loading.	33
Figure 44: Finished SAM Machine V1.0 Design.	33
Figure 45: Simple SAM Machine flowchart.	34
Figure 46: Expected machine outputs.	35
Figure 47: Pen drawing G-Code output.	35
Figure 48: Additive G-Code output.	36
Figure 49: Subtractive G-Code output.	36
Figure 50: Output error analysis.	37
Figure 24: M&S Power supply components and voltmeters.	45
Figure 25: M&S Controlling components.	46
Figure 26: M&S User interacting components.	47
Figure 27: M&S Test job code design.	48

Figure 28: M&S xyz Steppers digital analysis on a test job.	49
Figure 33: Assembly design sketch.	50
Figure 34: Control block system dimensions.	51
Figure 35: Control block parts and orientation.	52
Figure 36: Control block views and assembly.....	53
Figure 37: Machine block dimensions and tolerances.	54
Figure 38: Machine block parts and orientation.	55
Figure 39: Machine block views and assembly.....	56

Table of tables

Table 1: comparison of various software platforms.	15
Table 2: Power supply comparison.	17
Table 3: Microcontrollers comparison.	18
Table 4: Budget.	42
Table 5: Working schedule.	43

List of equations used

Equation i	12
Equation ii	12
Equation iii.....	13
Equation iv	13
Equation v	13
Equation vi	20
Equation vii.....	20
Equation viii.....	20
Equation ix	20
Equation x	20
Equation xi	21
Equation xii.....	21
Equation xiii.....	24
Equation xiv.....	25
Equation xv	25
Equation xvi.....	25
Equation xvii.....	25

Abbreviations used

Abbreviation	Meaning
CNC	Computer Numerical Control
NC	Numerical Control
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CAM	Computer Aided Manufacturing
FMS	Flexible Manufacturing Systems
AI	Artificial Intelligence
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
US	United States of America
SLA	Stereolithography Apparatus
SLS	Selective Laser Sintering
PLC	Programmable Logic Control
CPU	Central Processing Unit
AAC	Automatic Adaptive Control
3D	Three-Dimension
2D	Two-Dimension
PTP	Point-to-Point interpolation
CPP	Continuous Path Programming
BLU	Basic Length Units
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
DC	Direct Current
AC	Alternating Current
PIC	Peripheral Interface Controller
RISC	Reduced Instruction Set Computing
AVR	Advanced Virtual RISC
USB	Universal Serial Bus
RMS	Root Mean Square
LCD	Liquid Crystal Display

List of softwares used

- I. Labcenter Electronics Proteus
- II. Autodesk Inventor 3D
- III. Arduino IDE
- IV. MathWorks MATLAB

1. INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing has evolved over the years from Stone Age, through bronze and Iron Age until the time of industrial revolution in the 18th century, when there was a great leap in terms of productivity and quality. It was not until in the 20th century when the elements of organization and management of human resource termed as "scientific management" were studied and implemented for more economical manufacturing. The largest manufacturing industries in the 18th and 19th centuries were textile industries. In the 20th century, however, these were overtaken by the automobile and marine industry. During the first and the second world wars (1914-1918 and 1939-1945), there was a rapid demand for manufactured goods, especially for the military. This was a major stimulant for development of new materials and manufacturing technology. The demand for manufactured goods also rose rapidly with the fast growing world population. The need for standardization and interchangeability was met by use of jigs, fixtures and gauges in mass production of items. Automation of several processes was achieved through the use of dedicated mechanical systems. In the 1950's and later, there was a sharp rise in demand for more complex parts as well as a much larger variety. Mass production system was not capable of meeting the demand for larger variety due to the high cost of change over. Fortunately, the digital computer was invented around this time and it was readily adopted to machine tools. The numerical control (NC) machine tools were invented and these replaced the need for coordinated control of skilled machine operators. Since then, the use of computers has increased tremendously in the manufacturing.

In manufacturing today, computers are used in NC machining, robotics, Computer aided design (CAD), Computer Aided Manufacturing (CAM), Flexible Manufacturing Systems (FMS), Adaptive control systems, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and expert systems. They are used in planning and control of the manufacturing processes. This has encouraged the automation of the processes for faster and more economical production. (Groover, 2008)

The development of Subtractive-Additive Machine can be traced back to the invention and development of CNC machines and 3D Printers. Invention of NC (Numerical

Controlled) machine happened in 1940s-1950s by John T. Parsons. The NC was a breakthrough invention that led the way towards modern automated machines. Together with Frank L. Stulen, Parsons first utilized computer methods to crack machining setbacks, especially interpolation of curves.

The first published account of a printed solid model was made by Hideo Kodama of Nagoya Municipal Industrial Research Institute in 1982. The first working 3D printer was created in 1984 by Charles W. Hull of 3D Systems Corp. But it was only a 3D Printer and had not incorporated CNC machine functionalities. Therefore one has to buy both a 3D Printer and a CNC machine in order to perform additive and subtractive operations.

In the current industries, demand for both CNC and 3D Printers has increased majorly due to increased accuracy demand especially in complex product production.

This project aims to combine the two machine operations to be in one machine. This shall have utility in modern industrial, academic and economic function. (Chang T. , 2005)

The Subtractive-Additive Machine is a machine that generally uses a computer program and a controller to cause coordinated mechanical motions expedient in demonstration of machining or in the production of a component.

Normally, the subtractive and additive work is done by two separate machines namely; the Computer Numerical Control (CNC) for subtractive work and the 3D-Printer for additive work. The integration of these two machines gives rise to the Subtractive-Additive Machine.

One of the characteristics that distinguish man from animal is the ability to use tools and skills to make items. Manufacturing is the transformation of raw materials into usable products. It entails the skillful use of tools and self-organization in producing useable and saleable products so as to achieve a better standard of living. The basic purpose of any manufacturing industry is to create wealth, thus improving the quality of life.

1.1 Problem statement

In modern manufacturing and production, at times it's required that subtractive and additive work be done to produce a product. This is common especially in precise complex products where a product comprises of different materials, for example, wood and plastic. In this case, one has to do subtractive work using CNC and then do the

additive work using the 3D Printer or opt to do either of the two, but never both on the same machine. Subtractive-Additive Machine should do both subtractive and additive work in whichever way instructed.

In addition, students learn principles such as computer aided manufacturing (CAM) and additive process in printed circuit boards (PCB) in a specialized production machine shop on machines whose combined cost (CNC and 3D Printer) is high (\$50,000-70,000). A low-cost substitute in the hands of students will grant them comfortable environment to learn to program CNC and 3D Printers without risking several thousands of dollars of damage. This means that both concepts of additive and subtractive machining will be captured by one person.

1.2 Objectives

1.2.1 Main Objective

The main objective of this project is to develop a Subtractive-Additive Machine model demonstrating how subtractive and additive work can be done on the same machine at low cost.

1.2.2 Specific Objectives

The specific objective is to ensure the following components are manifested:

1. Milling machine model (subtractive).
2. 3D Printer model (additive).
3. Only 3-axes machine.

To ensure that the above is achieved in the same machine, more objectives were set;

- ❖ Design and develop a computer program that interacts with the user to instruct how the machine runs depending on the part to be produced the graphical user interface (SAM machine GUI software).
- ❖ Design and develop a control block, a set of contiguous subsystems adjoining to act as a single unit, capable of accepting the computer program and driving the motors accordingly on powering.
- ❖ Design and develop a Subtractive-Additive Machine block capable of showing how subtractive and additive work can be done on one machine.

- ❖ Integrating the computer program, control block and the machine block named above at a low cost.

1.2.3 Scope of the project

This project shall cover up to achieving straight machine tool movement using point-to-point method.

1.3 Justification

Industrialization is one of the factors that shall greatly contribute to the achievement of Kenyan vision 2030. As a developing country, much monetary resources get drained through purchase of machines from other countries like China, Germany and others. This also calls for experts from the same countries to operate, troubleshoot or repair especially for complex machines. It would be of great significance to substitute these machines with locally made ones, now that costs incurred in imports (machines and skills) would be channeled to Kenyans' core sectors like agriculture.

Modernization of the existing industries is a subject of substance. It gives rise to machines that are easier to use, much less human interaction, better power consumption and of low cost. The development of a low cost Subtractive-Additive Machine seeks to execute and bring into realization of these benefits in industries performing subtractive and additive machining.

Once fabricated, this machine can be used as a learning kit to train students on the principles of machining and manufacturing to mechatronics engineering students. Students learn operations of these machines in a specialized production machine shop on machines whose combined cost (CNC and 3D Printer) is high. A low-cost substitute in the hands of students will grant them comfortable environment to learn about and to program CNC and 3D Printers without risking several thousands of dollars of damage. This will give them a chance to control and also experiment hence preparing them for both academia and practical work in industry.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

There have been continued developments in these two separate machines but not in a machine combining both CNC and 3D Printers. This is as explained. There were a number of key developments in CNC. During the 1960's: Standard G-Code Language for Part Programs. The origin of G-code dates back to Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), around 1958, where it was a language used in the MIT Servomechanisms Laboratory. The Electronic Industry Alliance standardized g-code in the early 1960's. (CNC Cookbook, Inc., 2010-2014)

Computer Aided Design (CAD) came into its own and started rapidly replacing paper drawings and draftsmen during the 60's. By 1970, CAD was a decent sized industry with players like Intergraph and Computer vision. Minicomputers became available in the 60's and made CNC machines both cheaper and more powerful.

By 1970, the economies of most Western countries had slowed and employment costs were rising. With the 60's, having provided the firm technology foundation that was needed, CNC took off and began steadily displacing older technologies such as hydraulic tracers and manual machining.

United States of America (US) companies had largely launched the CNC revolution, but they had been overly focused on the high end. The Germans were the first to see the opportunity to reduce prices of CNC, and by 1979 the Germans were selling more CNC than the US companies. The Japanese repeated the same formula to an even more successful degree and had taken the leadership away from the Germans just one year later, by 1980. In 1971, the 10 largest CNC companies were all US companies, but by 1987, only Cincinnati Milacron was left and they were in 8th place.

Currently we have cheaper and better CNC compared with those of 1980's. This due increased use of microcontrollers.

The earliest development of 3-D printing technologies happened at Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) and at a company called 3D Systems. In the early 1990s,

MIT developed a procedure it trademarked with the name 3-D Printing, which it officially abbreviated as 3DP. As of February 2011, MIT has granted licenses to six companies to use and promote the 3DP process in its products.

3D Systems, based in Rock Hill, SC, has pioneered and used a variety of 3-D printing approaches since its founding in 1986. It has even trademarked some of its technologies, such as the stereolithography apparatus (SLA) and selective laser sintering (SLS), each described later in this article. While MIT and 3D Systems remain leaders in the field of 3-D printing, other companies such as Z Corporation, Objet Geometries have also brought innovative new products to market, building on these AM technologies.

3-D printing technology is being used to create finished products. The technology continues to improve in various ways, from the fineness of detail a machine can print to the amount of time required to clean and finish the object when the printing is complete. (Altintas, 2006)

Subtractive Additive Machine is meant for producing parts depending on what has been drawn on a CAD program and materials specified. There are diverse reasons as to why one would use additive method or even subtractive method. These include cost, time and accuracy. This machine shall provide a comfortable environment for either subtractive or additive work.

As explained in the methodology, a program shall be loaded into the microcontroller. This program shall contain the electronic description of the part to be produced. The microcontroller shall then give the respective signals to the motor drivers. On receiving the control signals from the microcontroller, motor drivers shall produce pulses just right to move the stepper motors to make the desired product.

2.2 Components of Numerical Control Machine

In addition to the machine frame and other features found in conventional machines, a typical Numerical control machine has the following components:

- I. **System Controller:** This consists of a mechanism for reading the software and converting the coding into machine instructions. The controller is the heart of the NC operation. There are different types of control programs;
 - Sequential control e.g. for perforated paper-tape
 - Programmable logic control (PLC) - a solid state device with a Central Processing Unit (CPU) interacting with I/O devices to monitor motion.
 - Automatic adaptive control (AAC) - continuously adjusts parameters for improvement
 - Numerical control - prerecorded written symbolic instructions.
- II. **Operator's Console:** This contains the necessary control for operating the machine manually. It could be a swinging cabinet, a rolling cabinet or an overhanging pendant. It offers the facility for setting up workpieces.
- III. **Magnetic controls cabinet:** Contains starting switches and magnetic relays for controlling the flow of electrical power to the pumps, spindle motor, etc. The relays and switches are controlled by the signals from the controller.
- IV. **Hydraulic pump:** This supplies fluid power for operating hydraulic motors attached to the lead screws for table movements. Note: Lead screws are, in some machines driven by electric motors. (Altintas, 2006)

2.3 Control Loops

CNC systems require motor drives to control both the position and the velocity of the machine axes. Each axis must be driven separately and follow the command signal generated by the NC control. There are two ways to activate the motor drives: use the open-loop system or the closed-loop system. The following sections will describe these two systems.

2.3.1 Open loop control

In general, an open loop control is a system where the output variables have no effect on the control of the input. In the open loop system, a device is instructed to move to a certain location, but the control unit does not ascertain that the device reaches the predetermined location.

Open-loop principles are also employed in the use of computers to manipulate electric or electro-hydraulic stepping motors for machine tool control. Discrete signals feed into the control unit, and instructions move to the stepping motor drive unit. One pulse input to the motor drives turns it through one step. The main variables in the open-loop

control deal with the stepping motor. These are the step angle, angle of rotation and rotational speed of the motor. The drive to the machine element may be a leadscrew, ball-bearing screw, rack and pinion or a pinion belt drive mechanism.

Open Loop- Programmed instructions are fed into the controller through an input device. These instructions are then converted to electrical pulses (signals) by the controller and sent to the servo amplifier to energize the servo motors. The cumulative number of electrical pulses determines the distance each servo drive will move, and the pulse frequency determines the velocity.

Figure 1: Open loop control block diagram.

Figure 2: Open loop control system.

2.3.2 Closed loop control

In order to completely automate a process of a machine tool, it is necessary to employ control systems that can compare the desired set of results with the actual results, and take corrective action. This is the essence of closed-loop feedback systems. Although open-loop control is simple and relatively cheap, it is not as accurate as closed-loop system.

In a closed-loop control system, the machine motion is normally actuated by servo motors and is monitored by a feedback unit that may be electronic, mechanical or optical. The feedback subsystem in a closed-loop system monitors continuously, the actual output and corrects any discrepancy from the programmed input.

The feedback subsystem could be either analog or digital. The analog systems measure the variation of physical variables such as position and velocity in terms of voltage levels. Digital systems monitor output variations by means of electrical pulses. The unit transmits position signals through the feedback signal circuit to the control unit where the signals are compared continuously with program signals. The command signal is fed through an amplifier to actuate the drive motor until the difference between the command signal and the actual slide position reaches zero. When the error signal is zero, the machine movements are at the exact or very close to the positions commanded.

Figure 3: Closed loop block diagram.

Figure 4: Closed loop control system.

2.4 Nomenclature for axes coordinate system

A universal standard axis system is employed. The Cartesian coordinate system is the most common system used to define a point in space. Each machine tool has a standard coordinate axis system, which allows the part programmer to define unambiguously the sequence of operations and movements of the machine tool, cutting tool and part. Machine tool construction is based on two or three perpendicular axes of motion and an axis of rotation. The basic convention is that the axis of the main machine spindle, whether it is the axis of the tool spindle or the axis about which the workpiece rotates, is denoted as the Z-axis. The other axes are then designated accordingly. See Figure below: (Bedworth, 1991)

Figure 5: Right-hand rule.

Figure 6: Main axis and rotational axis coordinate system.

For the sign convention, The Z-axis is positive in the direction from the workpiece towards the tool-holder or the spindle.

For machine tools that do not possess a principle spindle, the Z-axis is perpendicular to the work-holding surface. Once the coordinate axis is known, the parts programmer may have the option of specifying the tool position relative to the origin of the coordinate axes. NC machines may specify the zero point as a fixed zero or floating point. In fixed zero, the origin is always located at the same point on the machine table and is the lower left hand corner. Locations are defined by positive X and Y coordinates. A floating point allows the zero point to be set at any position on the machine table. The floating point method is more common.

2.5 Types of programming and interpolation

Numerical control programming can be classified into two categories: Point-to-Point (PTP) and continuous path system. In a PTP system, accurate positional control is required only to place the spindle, workpiece or other machine members in fixed positions for such operations as spot welding, drilling, boring, reaming or tapping. In between these positions, the only requirement is that the machine members move from one point to another without regard to the path taken. Since this movement from one point to the next is non-machining, it is made as rapidly as possible to reduce idle time. Movements in more than one axis may take place simultaneously (with separate controls) or sequentially (consumes more time). Though the path taken between the two points is generally not important, care must be taken to avoid collision with workpiece or fixture. In order to avoid errors due to backlash, it is advisable to approach a point always from the same direction along any axis. PTP is extensively used on machines that can move in one direction only. In some cases, PTP method is used to machine a straight line and a contour. See example below. In such cases, the number of steps determines how close the actual profile is to the specified profile. In order to get much closer to the specified line, much smaller step sizes will be needed and hence, a much longer program. (Chang T. e., 2005)

Figure 7: Point to point system.

For a continuous path system, the motion is controlled on more than one axis continuously and simultaneously. The machine controls not only the destinations, but also the paths through which the tool reaches these destinations. The cutting tool contacts the workpiece as coordinate movements take place. This system, which is also known as contouring system, is typically used in milling, grinding, turning, flame cutting and pocketing operations.

The main difference between continuous path programming (CPP) and PTP is the interpolation routine. The problem is to provide control for the tool continuously, which requires changes in two or more axes simultaneously, as the machining progresses.

Figure 8: Continuous path system.

Suppose in figure above, the length of the segment MN is 100 mm, and the movement to be made is from M to N. The displacement in x - direction will be given by;

Displacement, $d = 100 \cos(\theta)$ Equation i

$d = 100 \times \cos(30) = 86.60mm$ Equation ii

While that in y - direction has to be;

$$d = 100 \times \sin(30) = 50\text{mm} \dots \dots \text{Equation iii}$$

This type of cut requires the two driving motors to run simultaneously at two different speeds. This contouring system is certainly more expensive than the PTP system. The control of the travel rate in two or more directions, proportional to the distance moved is called linear interpolation. The shape produced is the result of a series of straight-line machining moves programmed in sufficient quantity to give an acceptable comparison between the designed shape and the actual shape. Let v_f be the desired velocity in the direction MN. Then the velocities along the two axes, v_x and v_y are;

$$v_x = \frac{\Delta x}{\sqrt{(\Delta x^2 + \Delta y^2)}} v_f \dots \dots \text{Equation iv}$$

$$v_y = \frac{\Delta y}{\sqrt{(\Delta x^2 + \Delta y^2)}} v_f \dots \dots \text{Equation v}$$

Where; Δx and Δy are the displacements along the x and y axes, respectively.

In linear interpolation for a circular surface, several thousand discrete points connected by straight lines would be required. Most machine control units however have a circular interpolator, in which the programming for a circular path is the end points of the arc, the radius, the arc center and the direction of the cutter. Example:

G02G17x56.5z70.0R65.5

The circular interpolator breaks up the span into the smallest straight line resolution units (Basic Length Units (BLU)) available in the control. The control computes and generates the controlling signal to achieve the required movements. Another type of interpolation is the parabolic interpolation for free-form surfaces. This usually requires generation of points for cutter paths, through a computer program.

2.6 Circular interpolation

If an NC controller does not have built-in functions for complicated geometries such as circles, parabolas etc., and these geometries can be approximated using an offline interpolation procedure. The main task in this case would be to determine the number of interpolation points that would guarantee the desired results in terms of tolerances. Most computer assisted part programming languages have subroutines for automatically calculating these points. Interpolation can be used to produce curves and circular or parabolic arcs to very close tolerances. Circular interpolation is performed by specifying an inner, outer or total tolerance, each of which is the maximum allowable deviation between the desired curve and the actual line. (Altintas, 2006), (Bedworth, 1991)

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Outline

This project is divided into three major parts to make it easy to implement. These parts are:

- Software
- Electronics
- Mechanical

Each of these parts was handled in the following processes;

I. Architecture

Constitute the basic visualization of the planned construction of the system. This was accomplished by means of making a sketch or a block diagram.

II. Requirements and Component selection

In this process, required parameters were identified. Different components available were selected to facilitate the design process.

III. Design

This is the final process whereby analysis and or programming were done. Professional drawings and necessary simulation also carried out.

3.2 Software part

The part to be produced was drawn in CAD software. The necessary coordinates was hence known. The user input those coordinates into the developed main program in G-code format or just browse and upload. The program was then loaded into the microcontroller. The microcontroller gave appropriate signals to the drivers. Drivers were able to in turn produce just the right pulses for the job.

3.2.1 Machine software-program architecture

The block diagram below illustrates the machine software architecture.

Figure 9: machine software-program architecture.

3.2.2 Machine software requirements

The software used must fulfill the following requirements for ease of operation;

- ✓ Able to run in available windows XP, 7, 8 or Linux platforms.
- ✓ Easy to learn and run.
- ✓ Can be stopped easily.

From the summary in the table below, we used Arduino IDE which met all of our requirements. We also used Matlab to make user interface software.

	Java	Arduino IDE	Visual Basic	Matlab
Platforms	All	All	Windows	All
Free	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Open Source	Yes	Yes	No	No
Easy Development	No	Yes	No	Yes
Student awareness	No	Yes	No	Yes

Table 1: comparison of various software platforms.

While many software packages available today meets the requirements of this project, keeping the software beginner-friendly eliminated many options and this helped to capture the concept easily.

3.2.3 Machine software design

In the design below, Arduino IDE software has been used to program the motion of a single axis. It shows how one axis shall be made to move according to the required product shape. To have the other axis move, similar programming shall be done to instruct the other axes to move accordingly. This calls for a change in the program every time a different product is ordered.

```
1 //To make a line say, along Y-axis, then stop;  
2 #include <Stepper.h>  
3 //Assume the motor driver has:ENA,ENB_logics;  
4 //IN1,IN2,IN3,IN4_interrups;  
5 //Depending on the number of motor steps;  
6 #define STEPS 200  
7 //No. of motor steps and pins it's attached  
8 //to needs to be specified;  
9 Stepper stepper(STEPS,2,3,4,5);  
10 void setup()  
11 {  
12 //Then setup code;  
13 stepper.setSpeed(300);  
14 pinMode(10,OUTPUT);  
15 pinMode(9,OUTPUT);  
16 digitalWrite(10,HIGH);  
17 digitalWrite(9,HIGH);  
18 stepper.step(100);  
19 delay(500);
```

Figure 10: Machine software design.

The highlighted command above is majorly responsible for the move taken by the machine tool, in this case a straight line in +Y direction. Depending on the product-shape required this part may change while the basic software design remains similar.

3.3 Electronics part

A control block was designed to have the following major parts:

- I. A resident microcontroller that receives the program from the computer and then sends necessary signals to the motor drivers.
The microcontroller can also receive an interrupt signal from the machine block limit switches, in case any of the axes hit the end.
- II. Motor drivers that receives the send logic signals from the microcontroller and consequently gives appropriate pulses to the stepper motors.
- III. A power supply to provide the three drivers with 12V DC, which in turn provide to motors in pulses according to the program instructions.
- IV. A program breaker circuit that stops the program uploads immediately the main power goes off.
- V. A cooling fan that blows out any kind of heating in the control block.
- VI. A set of control switches that control the machine block.

3.3.1 Machine electronics architecture

The electronics involved was connected as shown in the sketch below. This gives a visual overview of how we constructed the control block.

Figure 11: Machine electronics architecture.

3.3.2 Machine electronics requirements

This includes; the power supply, microcontroller and the motor drivers.

3.3.2.1 Power supply governing parameters

- ✓ An average value of load voltage of not less than 12V since our motors are rated 12V.
- ✓ An average value of load current of not less than 1.2A, for our motors operates within the range of 1.2A to 3A.
- ✓ Circuit efficiency of not less than 70%.
- ✓ A load ripples voltage of not more than 6V.

We used a regulated power supply whose terminal voltage is not affected by load.

Power Supply		
Battery	Rectified (AC to DC)	
	Unregulated	Regulated
Includes Dry cells and Battery cells	Mains supply needed	Mains supply needed
Portable	Relatively portable	Relatively portable
Ripple free	May have ripples	May have ripples
Low voltage and current	Voltage and current designed as needed	Voltage and current designed as needed
Need frequent replacement	No replacement needed	No replacement needed
Expensive	Cheaper	Less expensive
Voltage decreases with time	Terminal voltage affected by load	Voltage not affected by load

Table 2: Power supply comparison.

3.3.2.2 Microcontroller governing parameters

- ✓ Programmed through USB Port.
- ✓ At least 4 KB Flash/Data memories.
- ✓ Clock speed of around 10MHz would be sufficient.
- ✓ Available and easy-to-use development board.
- ✓ Available compiler.
- ✓ Easy code transfer between microcontrollers.
- ✓ Less expensive microcontroller; easy to replace.

There exist a number of microcontrollers in the market but we needed to choose one. A careful compromise was established such that a powerful yet low-cost, easy-to-program microcontroller is used. The main providers are the Microchip Peripheral Interface Controller (PIC) family and Atmel Advanced Virtual RISC (AVR) family. Both essentially satisfy the above listed requirements. Let's narrow down our choice in a table of comparison:

		Microchip PIC family	Atmel AVR family
Package		Can do prototyping projects well	Can do prototyping projects well
Prices (Chips)	8-Pin:	PIC12F629 (\$1.29)	ATtiny 13 (\$1.40)
	20-Pin:	PIC16F628 (\$3.35)	ATtiny 2313 (\$2.26)
	40-Pin:	PIC18F452 (\$10.35)	ATmega 32 (\$8.17)
Architecture (Chips)		Varying; hard code transfer	Similar; easy code transfer
Compiler		Available but not free	Free and high quality
Development boards		BASIC Stamp with RS232 Converter (\$44)	Arduino with USB Connector (\$32)
Support		Full featured website	Website with sample projects

Table 3: Microcontrollers comparison.

Following the summary above, we used the Atmel AVR family of microcontrollers and Arduino with USB connector development board.

3.3.2.3 Motor drivers governing parameters

- ✓ Operating Voltage of at least 12V
- ✓ Drives at least 1 stepper motor
- ✓ Max current of at least 2A per channel
- ✓ Free running stop and brake function
- ✓ Logic power supply of 5v
- ✓ Can withstand temperature of around 100°C

Most of the available drivers such as Easy-Drivers, L293 and L298 essentially satisfy the above minimum requirements but we used L298 since it's the only with best current operation with the range of 2A to 4A. It also has an operating voltage range of 4V to 35V and a temperature range of -25 to +135.

3.3.3 Machine electronics design

3.3.3.1 Power supply design

In regulated power supply, DC power supply terminal voltage remains almost constant regardless of the amount of current drawn from it. An unregulated supply can be converted into a regulated power supply by adding a voltage regulating circuit to it.

Figure 12: Regulated power supply.

To utilize both half-cycles of the transformer input, we used single-phase full-wave rectifier. Its configuration is illustrated;

Figure 13: single-phase full-wave rectifier.

We used power electronics knowledge to design our power supply as shown below;

$$Vl(dc) = \text{Average value of load voltage} = 12V$$

$$Il(dc) = \text{Average value of load current (dc component)} = 2A$$

$$Il(ac) = \text{ac component of load current}$$

$$Il = \text{Load current (rms)}$$

$$\eta = \text{Circuit efficiency}$$

$$\gamma = \text{Ripple factor}$$

$$Vsm = \text{Maximum value of transformer secondary voltage}$$

$$ILM = \text{Maximum value of load current (peak)}$$

$$VB = \text{Threshold voltage of a diode} = 0.7V(\text{silicon})$$

$$Rl = \text{Load resistance}$$

$R_o = \text{Diode forward resistance} + \text{Silicon rectifier resistance}$

We needed to know;

- How much should our V_{sm} be?

$$Vl(dc) = \frac{2 \times V_{sm}}{\pi} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation vi}$$

Hence;

$$V_{sm} = \frac{Vl(dc) \times \pi}{2} = \frac{12 \times \pi}{2} = 18.85V$$

This means we can set the maximum value of our transformer secondary voltage to be around 19V.

- What will be the maximum value of load current ILM ?

$$Il(dc) = \frac{2 \times ILM}{\pi} = 0.6366 \times ILM \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation vii}$$

Hence;

$$ILM = \frac{Il(dc)}{0.6366} = \frac{2}{0.6366} = 3.1A$$

Approximately 3A is tolerable.

- What will be the efficiency of the circuit η ?

$$\eta = \frac{P_{dc}}{P_{in}} = \frac{(2 \times ILM / \pi)^2 \times (Rl)}{(ILM / \sqrt{2})^2 \times (R_o + Rl)} = \frac{4 \times ILM^2 / \pi^2 \times (Rl)}{\frac{1}{2} \times ILM^2 \times (R_o + Rl)} = \frac{8}{\pi^2} \times \frac{Rl}{R_o + Rl} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation viii}$$

But,

$$Vl(dc) = Il(dc) \times Rl \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation ix}$$

So,

$$Rl = \frac{Vl(dc)}{Il(dc)} = \frac{12}{2} = 6\Omega$$

And also,

$$ILM = \frac{V_{sm} - V_B}{R_o + Rl} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation x}$$

Thus;

$$R_o = \frac{V_{sm} - V_B}{I_{LM}} - R_l = \frac{19 - 0.7}{3} - 6 = 0.1\Omega$$

Hence;

$$\eta = 0.8106 \times \frac{6}{0.1 + 6} = 80\%$$

80% is well above our minimum requirement.

➤ What will be the RMS value of ripple voltage in our circuit design?

RMS value of ripple voltage = $\gamma \times V_l(dc)$ Equation xi

But,

$$\gamma = \frac{I_l(ac)}{I_l(dc)} = \frac{\sqrt{I_l^2 - I_l(dc)^2}}{I_l(dc)} = \frac{\sqrt{(I_{LM}/\sqrt{2})^2 - I_l(dc)^2}}{I_l(dc)} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation xii}$$

So,

$$\text{RMS value of ripple voltage} = \frac{\sqrt{(3/\sqrt{2})^2 - 2^2}}{2} \times 12 = 4.243V$$

This value is well below the maximum requirement.

We further simulated this design in Proteus Software. This is as shown below;

Figure 14: Power Supply Design.

An output voltage of 12.00V was recorded as shown above. Capacitors were added to smoothen the output and the voltage regulator was added to ensure a constant terminal voltage.

3.3.3.2 Microcontroller interfacing design

We used Arduino development board to load the program to the ATmega 328P. The interfacing was needed around the ATmega 328P to receive a program. This design was done in proteus software and the following virtual system model was captured:

Figure 15: Microcontroller interfacing design.

The results shown above also involved loading the program in the microcontroller and then simulating.

3.3.3.3 Motor drivers interfacing design

The L298 motor driver was interfaced as shown below;

Figure 16: Motor drivers interfacing design.

3.4.1 Machine mechanical architecture

The mechanical part was constructed as shown in the sketch below. This gives a basic overview of how we constructed the machine block as from the control block.

Figure 18: From control block to machine block.

3.4.2 Machine mechanical requirements

- ✓ Machine body made of wood to minimize on cost.
- ✓ Make table (Y axis) and the other axes as light and frictionless as possible.
- ✓ Assemble machine block in a way it would be easy to disassemble for illustration and learning purposes.
- ✓ Cover much distance with fewer revolutions for faster positioning.
- ✓ Resolution of around 0.3mm to 1mm would be sufficient for a demonstration.
- ✓ A stepper motor step angle of 1.8° ; to improve on resolution.

We used pinion and belt in place of a lead screw. This led to much distance covered within fewer motor revolutions. In addition, this mechanism was widely available and cheaper compared to lead screw.

3.4.3 Machine mechanical design

$$\text{Step angle, } \theta = 1.8^\circ$$

$$\text{Drive Pinion Diameter, } D = 8.47\text{mm}$$

$$\frac{\text{Steps}}{\text{rev}} = \frac{360}{\theta} \dots \dots \text{Equation xiii}$$

$$\frac{\text{Steps}}{\text{rev}} = \frac{360}{1.8} = 200 \frac{\text{Steps}}{\text{rev}} \left(\frac{\text{Pulses}}{\text{rev}} \right)$$

Suppose motor shaft is directly connected to the pinion of the pinion and belt drive for driving machine table.

One revolution of the motor causes a motion equal to the perimeter of the pinion.

Perimeter, $P = \pi \times D$ Equation xiv

$$P = \pi \times 8.47 = 26.61mm$$

It's important to determine resolution; how closely the table's position can be controlled. Suppose we want to move the table at 120 mm/min. What would be the rotational speed of the motor and the pulse frequency?

Resolution, $R = \frac{P}{\frac{Steps}{rev}}$ Equation xv

$$R = \frac{26.61}{200} = 0.13305mm \text{ increments}$$

This is well below 1mm minimum requirement.

To achieve the table speed of 120 mm/min, how much will be the pinion speed (and hence the motor speed)?

Speed $\left(\frac{rev}{min}\right)$, $RPM = \frac{table \ speed}{P}$ Equation xvi

$$RPM = \frac{table \ speed}{P} = \frac{120}{26.61} = 4.5 \text{ RPM}$$

Pulse frequency, $Pf = \frac{motor \ RPM \times Pulses/rev}{60}$ Equation xvii

$$Pf = \frac{4.5 \times 200}{60} = 15 \text{ Pulses/sec}$$

From the above case study, the following can be deduced:

- With fewer revolutions per minute, much distance will have been covered by the axis in motion. Hence less power will be used to make the required motion.
- Less time will be required to position the table or the tool to its required position, for example, one revolution of the motor will move the table by 26.61mm.
- Low Pulse Frequency is required for any desired motion.

A mechanical design of the machine was modeled using Autodesk Inventor software. The results were as shown below.

Figure 19: Machine mechanical design assembly.

From the model above, X axis carries the Z axis but the Y axis stands alone.

The model was exploded to show the all parts that constituted the assembly. These parts are as shown below.

Figure 20: Machine block parts.

The output below was also captured to show some of the machine block views.

Figure 21: Various machine block views.

3.5 Overall machine operation flow chart

Full machine operation and the commands execution process are as summarized in the following flow chart. It captures all the basic steps followed in a normal machine operation.

Figure 22: Overall machine operation.

4. VIRTUAL IMPLEMENTATION

To make progress faster with certainty, we decided to invest in modeling and simulation (M&S) which ensures that the project components remain in good condition, free from risks involved when carrying out imprecise experimentation. When designing, we used M&S to optimize the systems by making necessary changes and obtaining good results safely. One is able to understand the systems and the sub-systems in detail and in multiple views. Time could as well be slowed or made to move faster all in this virtual environment.

We developed our circuit designs in Proteus Virtual System Modeling environment and obtained the outputs as follows:

Figure 23: X stepper moving clockwise 16 steps/rev.

By dividing each t by 2 we get 16ts which represent the 16 steps that this stepper must take to complete a revolution. We used 16 steps/rev only in simulation for visual clarity otherwise we shall implement using 200 steps/rev for better resolution. The difference

between moving clockwise and counterclockwise in terms of control can be seen by comparing figure above with figure below.

Figure 24: Y stepper moving counterclockwise 16 steps/rev.

You notice that for steps in a clockwise direction; $\begin{bmatrix} 0110 \\ 0101 \\ 1001 \\ 1010 \end{bmatrix}$ is send to out $\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \\ 4 \end{bmatrix}$ four times to make 16 steps for one revolution while in a counterclockwise direction; $\begin{bmatrix} 1001 \\ 0101 \\ 0110 \\ 1010 \end{bmatrix}$ is send to out $\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \\ 4 \end{bmatrix}$ four times to make 16 steps for one revolution in the opposite direction. 1 represent +12V and 0 represent 0V. To complete one revolution which is 16 steps, it will require the order to continually change as illustrated in figures above until the 16th step.

Figure 25: Control of stepper motor.

To make the user-machine interaction friendly, we designed graphical user interface software in a MATLAB environment. The exercise involved designing the graphical user interface software in such a way that it is stand-alone, can allow the usage of machine instructions (G-Code) both by loading a file using a browse button or even manual machine programming directly from the interface. This implies that SAM Machine software reads G-Code and gives you a provision to edit or write the code manually then loads the code to the microcontroller. The user interface software should also allow a change in COM port, show or pop out information messages such as warning, loading or an advice in the event of an error and also have a start and stop button. The design shown below was found appropriate.

Figure 26: Designed user interface software.

The software establishes the link with the machine and allows the user to comfortably send the instructions to the machine. It also assists in processing the raw instructions (G-Code) from the user.

5. RESULTS

This section presents the results of the practical implementation of this project. This is helpful especially when it comes to latter improvements since it gives clearer information about what it takes to have the actual model working as planned. This section shall be composed of photos for a clear illustration and will present processes involved in three parts; mechanical, electrical and software.

Figure 27: Machine block wood parts and Control block parts.

Figure 28: Assembled machine block.

Figure 29: Soldering, Wiring, Labeling and Testing involved.

Figure 30: Machine software GUI design captured when loading.

To home the machine, turn the machine to Fix mode. Move all axes to the positive extreme such that all axes just touches the limit switch. Turn the machine to Normal mode. Run the homing G-Code.

Figure 31: Finished SAM Machine V1.0 Design.

This machine was supposed to do some subtractive and additive works at a low cost. The way in which the machine did the job can be best illustrated by the use of a flow chart:

Figure 32: Simple SAM Machine flowchart.

The figure below shows a way in which the machine outputs were expected.

Figure 33: Expected machine outputs.

Below are the outputs that were got and discussion relating to the results as compared to the expected output shown above. The machine gave three kinds of outputs; Pen drawing, Subtractive and Additive G-Code outputs:

Figure 34: Pen drawing G-Code output.

To achieve additive output, Z axis was moving up in steps to make layers while in subtractive output, Z was moving down in steps to subtract layers. For pen drawing

output, Z only moved down once then up after the drawing is complete; no layer subtraction or addition.

Figure 35: Additive G-Code output.

Figure 36: Subtractive G-Code output.

Videos showing how the above results were achieved can be found in <http://engineeringmechatronics.com> or in 'engineering mechatronics' Google+ YouTube channel.

5.1 Errors and Analysis

We analyzed the results above in the following discussion.

Figure 37: Output error analysis.

The 'error A' shown in figure 48 above was observed and recorded. This error is similar to 'error C' only that 'error A' is greater than 'error C'. Error C is found in Y-axis, Table while error A is found in X-axis. Error A is not consistent and doesn't propagate since it only occurs in the beginning, for around 22mm then disappears. This error is repeatable since it occurred the same way within the first 22mm in all tests. Error C is consistent and propagates with length and it is also repeatable. Error B only occurred once.

Why error A?

- ✓ X-axis bearing misalignment.
- ✓ X-axis rail bending.
- ✓ Production tolerances not achieved.
- ✓ Natural variance.

Why error B?

- ✓ Production tolerances not achieved.
- ✓ Vibrations found in the table.
- ✓ Tool vibrations.

Why error C?

- ✓ Y-axis bearing misalignment.
- ✓ Y-axis production tolerances not achieved.
- ✓ Natural variance.

Errors found in Z-axis:

- ✓ Pinion gear offset.
- ✓ Gear slip.
- ✓ Vibrations caused by motor rotating tool.

From figure 48; output error analysis, 20.2mm is achieved as a result of 200 steps or 30.3 as a result of 300 steps.

If 200 steps translate to 20.2mm, 1 step translate to $\frac{20.2}{200} = 0.101mm$ this is close to 0.13305mm resolution value seen in equation xv in page 31.

5.2 Machine features

This section presents what machine was capable of doing, how it was handled and skills needed if a student wanted to make one him(her)self.

- The machine has two major modes; Fix mode and Normal mode.
- Without using a computer: you only need to plug in 240V 50Hz mains to the control block and 5V from USB port to the microcontroller unit. The only functionality in this case is found in Fix mode, whereby machine control is done manually from the control panel using control knobs. While in 'Fix mode', the machine shall not execute a G-Code instruction from the computer but shall store the instruction until the time you shall switch to 'Normal mode', unless it is interrupted by a limit switch or an emergency shutdown.
- With a computer: SAM Machine GUI software is needed. In this case, 'Normal mode' additional functionality is available. When the machine is working on a G-Code, it doesn't recognize Fix mode until it completes that task, unless it is interrupted by a limit switch or an emergency shutdown.
- Warning/Start up tone available.
- Emergency shutdown.
- Machine display available, which shows operation progress.

- Machine lighting available, which makes viewing easier as the machine performs its job.
- Control block cooling fan to ensure that heating is minimized.
- Speed control knob and also display contrast rheostat.
- Homing capability.

5.3 Machine caution

- Do not move any axis manually.
- Pull not the connector cable.
- Open the machine only with an instructor.
- Cover not the fan.
- Use lighting only when necessary.
- Do not wash the machine.
- Home machine before use.

5.4 Skills used/needed

- Workshop technology.
- CAD/CAM.
- Engineering design.
- Measurement and instrumentation.
- Power electronics.
- Analog and digital electronics.
- Microprocessors and microcontrollers.
- Electrical installation.
- Control engineering.
- Programming MATLAB and Arduino IDE.
- Modeling and simulation.
- Serial communication.
- Project management.
- Team work and commitment.

5.5 Troubleshoots

- Connector failure which was removed all together.
- Wire internal disconnects which was replaced by a stronger wire.
- Pinion gear offset and x,y inaccuracy.
- All grounds connected.
- LCD lighting failure; power A and K terminals.
- Display data missing; ensure RW terminal is grounded.
- Slipping belt-pinion mechanism; tighten the mechanism.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion was drawn based on what was achieved relating to what was expected. Recommendation will highlight what needs to be done in the next stage of the development of SAM.

- ❖ A computer program that interacts with the user was designed and developed. This is the SAM Machine GUI software; it instructs how the machine runs depending on the part to be produced. This was best achieved by use of G-Code which called for a development of a microcontroller firmware that understands G-Code. The following are recommendations in this area:
 - 1) Improve this software such that it can simulate the final product before getting the actual product. This reduces waste in workpiece.
 - 2) Incorporate control panel within this software.
 - 3) Work on a software that reduce the loading/waiting time (1 min) before the machine could respond to G-Code instruction.
 - 4) Improve the firmware to the level that can accept G02/G03 and also decimal point numbers.
- ❖ A control block was designed and developed, which was capable of accepting the computer program and driving the motors accordingly on powering. This was successful as a result of coming up with the right power supply design that could supply the sufficient current and voltage (12V 3A) when needed regardless of the load. The right choice of the microcontroller was important since it need to communicate with the drivers and the computer; as illustrated in methodology section. The following are the recommendations in this area:
 - 1) The top cover of control block should be made of Perspex to allow one to see how the drivers activate the motors for easy learning.
 - 2) More advanced stepper motor drivers should be used to facilitate microstepping.
- ❖ A Subtractive-Additive Machine block was designed and developed which was capable of showing how subtractive and additive work can be done on one machine. The following recommendation was recorded:
 - 1) A more accurate pinion-belt mechanism should be used to move the rails.

- 2) A mechanism that cannot allow unintended manual axes movement is preferable.
 - 3) When making the control block achieving the specified tolerances in the engineering drawing is important.
 - 4) X-Z mechanism with actuators of a high speed torque compromise.
 - 5) For subtractive work, the motor rotating tool should have control and should have more torque to drill a hole on a mild steel workpiece.
 - 6) For additive work, a pump should be introduced to pump the fluid out with control.
- ❖ The computer program, control block and the machine block named above was integrated at a low cost. This was successful because making use of recycled materials such as wood pieces and parts from an old computer. The following recommendation was noted:
- 1) Use standard connectors when connecting between various blocks or sections.

6.1 Challenges

- Most essential subsystems were made from scratch of which we had a nodding acquaintance about how they should be made.
- Coming up with a firmware that accepts G-Code.
- Making the SAM Machine GUI software that reads and loads G-Code to the microcontroller. It shows you this progress and advices in the event of an error.
- It could take one minute waiting for G-Code to load.
- Coming up a control panel
- To demonstrate SAM Machine Subtractive-Additive functionality, precision especially in machine block was an essential requirement.
- The precise current and voltage was needed from the control block which called for accurate power supply design.
- The project had to be kept low-cost.
- Complex wiring and labeling.
- Making the whole machine in a way that every part can be opened safely for learning purposes or even repair.

BUDGET

SUBTRACTIVE-ADDITIVE MACHINE BUDGET					
No.	Item/Component	Specification	Quantity	Unit Cost	Total (Ksh)
1	Motor Driver	L298N	3	2000	6000
2	Stepper motor	Medium torque at least (50Ncm, 2A)	3	4000	12000
3	Microcontroller	Arduino Mega (Atmega2560 chip)	1	4500	4500
4	Limit Switches	Lightly on/off (high sensitivity)	6	30	180
5	Male connectors	Soft	46	2	92
6	Female connectors	Soft	50	2	100
7	Conductors	Soft connectors	1	50	50
8	LCD	HD44780 QC1602A v2.0 16X4	1	500	500
9	Printer Rails	Pinion and Belt	2	500	1000
10	DVD Drivers	Rack and Pinion	1	200	200
11	Transformer	Stepdown, 5A, 15V	3	700	2100
12	Diodes	1N4001	12	50	600
13	Capacitors	5000uF	3	500	1500
14	Capacitors	0.01uF	3	20	60
15	Resistor	680 Ohms	3	10	30
16	Transistor	2N3055	3	10	30
17	Zener Diode	12V	3	50	150
18	Power Cable	3 Pin plug (240v 50Hz 13A)	1	250	250
19	Junction Box	Standard	1	100	100
20	Perfboard	2.5(W) X 5(H) in	3	50	150
21	Solder	2M length	1	500	500
22	Soldering Gun/Iron	2 Pin (240v 13A)	1	500	500
23	Jumper wires	Soft	12	5	60
24	Potentiometer	4.7K Ohms	1	100	100
25	Resistor	10K Ohms	1	20	20
26	Male Breakaway Header	16 Pin	1	200	200
27	White Labels	2X3 Cm	1	300	300
28	Connectors	50 Pin (Male)	2	500	1000
29	Connectors	50 Pin (Female)	2	550	1100
30	Printing	Printing Cost	2	500	1000
31	Bearings	6202Rs	4	1000	4000
32	Wood	Oak	N/A	N/A	N/A
33	Nails	1in	N/A	N/A	N/A
34	Push Buttons	Lightly on/off (high sensitivity)	6	60	360
35	Switch	240V on/off	3	30	90
36	Marker Pen	Temporary (Red and Blue)	2	50	100
37	Screws	Wood Screws	N/A	N/A	N/A
	TOTAL (KSH)				38922

Table 4: Budget.

WORKING SCHEDULE

MONTH	May-14	Jun-14	Jul-14	Aug-14	Sep-14	Oct-14	Nov-14	Dec-14	Jan-15	Feb-15	Mar-15
ACTIVITY											
Project Research	■										
Project Proposal		■	■								
Software and Programming			■	■							
Electronics Implementation				■	■						
Mechanical Implementation					■			■			
Project Assembly								■	■		
Testing and Experimentation				■	■			■	■		
Reporting and Documentation					■			■	■	■	
Presentation				■				■	■	■	■

Table 5: Working schedule.

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APPENDIX 1: CIRCUIT DESIGNS AND ELECTRONICS SIMULATION OUTPUTS

Figure 38: M&S Power supply components and voltmeters.

Figure above is captured under simulation. The blue square dots show the grounded current. The +12v and +5v outputs is meant for use in the rest of M&S.

Figure 39: M&S Controlling components.

Figure above shows three stepper motor drivers for x,y and z respectively. It also shows a serial port equivalent, P1, and the microcontroller which already has a running program. The arrows and circular terminations are labeled as used elsewhere in the previous or next sheet(s).

Figure 40: M&S User interacting components.

Figure above was captured when operating in Normal Mode. The machine has two modes: Normal Mode; Mode Switch Closed [0] and Fix Mode; Mode Switch Open [1]. In Normal Mode, the machine does work as a result of program instruction received from a serial port. In Fix Mode, the machine does work as a result of someone pressing XYZ control knobs.

For it to operate in Normal Mode, it was given a test job in the form equivalent as shown in figure below:

```
Virtual Terminal
//SAM v1.0 Test Job G_Code Design

X20
Y-20
Z20
X-20
Y20
Z-20

X20
Y20
X-20
Y-20
X20
Z20
X-20
Z-20
Y20
Z20
Y-20
Z-20

X01 Y01

delay (250);

Y01 X01
```

Figure 41: M&S Test job code design.

Instruction in Figure above was executed under a G01,G21,G91 default conditions. The digital analysis was carried out on each four x,y,z stepper terminals and captured as shown below in figure below:

Figure 42: M&S xyz Steppers digital analysis on a test job.

We found M&S helpful in analyzing and predicting with certainty a possible outcome in our real implementation. The video illustrating how this simulation worked was embedded here: <http://engineeringmechatronics.wordpress.com>

For a better understanding of the analysis in figure 26 above, we shall zoom in the first x and y four stepper terminals (bipolar stepper) to see how the voltage reception is conceived in the coils to achieve a clockwise or anticlockwise motion.

APPENDIX 2: SAM MACHINE MECHANICAL DESIGNS

The mechanical drawing and design that was proposed happened to have very large dimensions and lacked important details such as where to put the control panel. We had to figure out how the full assembly of the real machine model would look like. This was first sketched in the design book to make the vague impression clearer. The sketch is shown in figure below.

Figure 43: Assembly design sketch.

Three components A, B, and C shown in the sketch in figure above represent the computer, the control block and the machine block physical appearance and its dimensions. This sketch was useful in producing a more comprehensive design as illustrated below.

PARTS LIST			
ITEM	QTY	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION
1	1	Left Solid1	280x145x15mm Oak Wood
2	1	Right Solid2	280x145x15mm+12.5usb sq hole Oak Wood
3	1	North Solid3	350x145x15mm Oak Wood+Power hole
4	1	South Solid4	350x145x15mm Oak Wood
5	1	Bottom Solid5	300x75x15mm Oak Wood
6	1	Bottom Solid6	300x75x15mm Oak Wood
7	1	Inner_Lock Solid7	290x7.5x7.5mm Oak Wood
8	1	Inner_Lock Solid8	247.5x7.5x7.5mm Oak Wood
9	1	Bottom_core Solid9	260x247.5x10mm Oak Wood
10	1	Left_core Solid10	240x120x15mm Oak Wood
11	1	Right_core Solid11	240x120x15mm Oak Wood
12	1	Arduino Mega 2560 Solid12	101.6x53.34x2mm Circuit Board
13	1	Rails Solid13	240x10x10mm Oak Wood; 12mm spacing
14	1	Slider Solid14	240x230x10mm Hard Plywood+2mm holes all around to screw in electronics
15	1	Top_cover Solid15	290x269.41x15mm Oak Wood+85mm Diameter hole for Cooling Fan
16	1	Junction_Box Solid16	85mm Diameter Plastic

Figure 45: Control block parts and orientation.

Figure 46: Control block views and assembly.

Figure 47: Machine block dimensions and tolerances.

PARTS LIST			
ITEM	QTY	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION
1	1	Back_Basement Solid1	360x120x20mm Oak Wood
2	1	Front_Basement Solid2	360x120x20mm Oak Wood
3	1	Right_Basement Solid3	400x120x20mm Oak Wood
4	1	Left_Basement Solid4	400x120x20mm Oak Wood
5	1	Support Solid5	305x80x20mm Oak Wood
6	1	Support Solid6	305x80x20mm Oak Wood
7	1	Support Solid7	305x80x20mm Oak Wood
8	1	Support Solid8	305x80x20mm Oak Wood
9	1	Basement_Support_Root Solid9	120x80x20mm Oak Wood
10	1	Basement_Support_Root Solid10	120x20x20mm Oak Wood
11	1	Basement_Support_Root Solid11	120x80x20mm Oak Wood
12	1	Basement_Support_Root Solid12	340x120x20mm Oak Wood
13	1	Basement_Support_Root Solid13	120x20x20mm Oak Wood
14	1	Basement_Support_Root Solid14	120x80x20mm Oak Wood
15	1	Basement_Support_Root Solid15	120x80x20mm Oak Wood
16	1	Basement_Support_Root Solid16	340x120x20mm Oak Wood
17	1	Basement_Bottom_Rest Solid17	440x130x20mm Oak Wood
18	1	Basement_Bottom_Rest Solid18	440x130x20mm Oak Wood
19	1	Table_Support Solid19	210x90x20mm Oak Wood
20	1	Table_Support Solid20	210x90x20mm Oak Wood
21	1	Table Solid21	210x199x10mm Hard plywood
22	1	Front_Cover Solid22	360x115x20mm Oak Wood
23	1	Back_Cover Solid23	360x115x20mm Oak Wood
24	1	Top_Support Solid24	500x180x20mm Oak Wood; remove 180x30x20mm
25	1	Control_Pannel_Bottom_Support Solid25	180x80x20mm Oak Wood
26	1	Control_Pannel_Side_Support Solid26	205x194.5x20mm Oak Wood; remove <77.8
27	1	Control_Pannel Solid27	180x169.79x10mm Hard Plywood
28	1	X-Axis_Rail Solid28	290x40x1.5mm Alluminium alloy
29	1	Z-Axis_Rail Solid29	53.11x41.12x10mm Oak Wood
30	1	Tool_Extruder_Housing Solid30	67.67x17.56mm Plastic housing
31	1	Control_Pannel_Back_Support Solid31	218.73x146.39x10mm Oak Wood

Figure 48: Machine block parts and orientation.

Figure 49: Machine block views and assembly.

APPENDIX 3: SAM MACHINE GUI SOFTWARE PROGRAM

```
function varargout = SAM_Machine(varargin)

% SAM_MACHINE MATLAB code for SAM_Machine.fig
%     SAM_MACHINE, by itself, creates a new SAM_MACHINE or
%     raises the existing
%     singleton*.
```

```

%
%       H = SAM_MACHINE returns the handle to a new SAM_MACHINE
or the handle to
%       the existing singleton*.
%
%       SAM_MACHINE('CALLBACK',hObject,eventData,handles,...)
calls the local
%       function named CALLBACK in SAM_MACHINE.M with the given
input arguments.
%
%       SAM_MACHINE('Property','Value',...) creates a new
SAM_MACHINE or raises the
%       existing singleton*. Starting from the left, property
value pairs are
%       applied to the GUI before SAM_Machine_OpeningFcn gets
called. An
%       unrecognized property name or invalid value makes
property application
%       stop. All inputs are passed to SAM_Machine_OpeningFcn
via varargin.
%
%       *See GUI Options on GUIDE's Tools menu. Choose "GUI
allows only one
%       instance to run (singleton)".
%
% See also: GUIDE, GUIDATA, GUIHANDLES

% Edit the above text to modify the response to help SAM_Machine

% Last Modified by GUIDE v2.5 29-Nov-2014 23:46:34

% Begin initialization code - DO NOT EDIT
gui_Singleton = 1;
gui_State = struct('gui_Name',       mfilename, ...
                  'gui_Singleton',  gui_Singleton, ...
                  'gui_OpeningFcn', @SAM_Machine_OpeningFcn,
                  ...
                  'gui_OutputFcn',  @SAM_Machine_OutputFcn, ...
                  'gui_LayoutFcn',  [] , ...
                  'gui_Callback',   []);
if nargin && ischar(varargin{1})
    gui_State.gui_Callback = str2func(varargin{1});
end

if nargout
    [varargout{1:nargout}] = gui_mainfcn(gui_State,
varargin{:});

```

```

else
    gui_mainfcn(gui_State, varargin{:});
end
% End initialization code - DO NOT EDIT

% --- Executes just before SAM_Machine is made visible.
function SAM_Machine_OpeningFcn(hObject, eventdata, handles,
varargin)
% This function has no output args, see OutputFcn.
% hObject    handle to figure
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
% handles    structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)
% varargin   command line arguments to SAM_Machine (see
VARARGIN)

% Choose default command line output for SAM_Machine
handles.output = hObject;

% Update handles structure
guidata(hObject, handles);

% UIWAIT makes SAM_Machine wait for user response (see UIRESUME)
% uiwait(handles.figure1);

% --- Outputs from this function are returned to the command
line.
function varargout = SAM_Machine_OutputFcn(hObject, eventdata,
handles)
% varargout  cell array for returning output args (see
VARARGOUT);
% hObject    handle to figure
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
% handles    structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)

% Get default command line output from handles structure
varargout{1} = handles.output;

function messages_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject    handle to messages (see GCBO)
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB

```

```

% handles      structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)

% Hints: get(hObject,'String') returns contents of messages as
text
%           str2double(get(hObject,'String')) returns contents of
messages as a double

% --- Executes during object creation, after setting all
properties.
function messages_CreateFcn(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject      handle to messages (see GCBO)
% eventdata    reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
% handles      empty - handles not created until after all
CreateFcns called

% Hint: edit controls usually have a white background on
Windows.
%           See ISPC and COMPUTER.
if ispc      &&      isequal(get(hObject,'BackgroundColor'),
get(0,'defaultUicontrolBackgroundColor'))
    set(hObject,'BackgroundColor','white');
end

function G_CodeMini_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject      handle to G_CodeMini (see GCBO)
% eventdata    reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
% handles      structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)

% Hints: get(hObject,'String') returns contents of G_CodeMini as
text
%           str2double(get(hObject,'String')) returns contents of
G_CodeMini as a double

% --- Executes during object creation, after setting all
properties.
function G_CodeMini_CreateFcn(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject      handle to G_CodeMini (see GCBO)
% eventdata    reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
% handles      empty - handles not created until after all
CreateFcns called

```

```

% Hint: edit controls usually have a white background on
Windows.
% See ISPC and COMPUTER.
if ispc && isequal(get(hObject,'BackgroundColor'),
get(0,'defaultUiControlBackgroundColor'))
    set(hObject,'BackgroundColor','white');
end

% --- Executes on button press in browse.
function browse_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject handle to browse (see GCBO)
% eventdata reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
% handles structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)
try
[filename pathname]=uigetfile({'*.txt'},'File Selector'); %browse
file
fullpathname=strcat(pathname, filename);%get path of the file
text=fileread(fullpathname); %read info inside
set(handles.G_CodeMini_Path, 'String',fullpathname) %display
fullpathname
set(handles.G_CodeMini, 'String',text) %display text

catch errorObj
    %If there's a prob, disp the error message.

errordlg(getReport(errorObj,'extended','hyperlinks','off'),'SAM_
Machine v1.0');
end

% --- Executes on button press in connect.
function connect_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject handle to connect (see GCBO)
% eventdata reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
% handles structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)
try

arduino = serial(get(handles.serial_port,'String'));
arduino.BaudRate=9600;

    h=waitbar(0,'Establishing hardware link...','Name','SAM
Machine v1.0');
    steps=1000;

```

```

        for step=1:steps
            waitbar(step/steps,h,sprintf('Establishing hardware
link...%.2f%%',step/steps*100));
            %pause(0.1);
        end
        delete(h)

fopen(arduino);

disp('Now Ready!')
disp(arduino)
fscanf(arduino);%initial start response

G_CodeMini = get(handles.G_CodeMini,'String');
drawnow;
fprintf(arduino,G_CodeMini);
disp('Value entered:')
disp('G_CodeMini')

%num_lines = size(G_CodeMini,1);
%persistent restart_pos;
%if isempty(restart_pos)
%    restart_pos=1;
%else
%    set(handles.connect,'String','connect');
%    set(handles.messages,'String','');
%end

%for i=restart_pos:num_lines
%    restart_pos = i+1;
%    line = G_CodeMini(i,:);
%    set(handles.current_line,'String',num2str(i));
%    action = handle_line(hObject, eventdata, handles,line);
%    drawnow;
%    fprintf(arduino,char(G_CodeMini(i,:)));
%    resp = fgetl(arduino);
%    if strcmp(action,'disconnect')
%        set(handles.connect,'String','Continue');
%        fclose(arduino);
%        return;
%    end
%end%

fprintf(arduino,G_CodeMini);
fclose(arduino);
disp('Now Closed!')
disp(arduino)

```

```

catch errorObj
    %If there's a prob, disp the error message.

errordlg(getReport(errorObj,'extended','hyperlinks','off'),'SAM_
Machine v1.0');
end

% --- Executes on button press in disconnect.
function disconnect_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject    handle to disconnect (see GCBO)
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
% handles    structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)

try

fclose(arduino);
disp('Now Closed!')
disp(arduino)

catch errorObj
    %If there's a prob, disp the error message.

errordlg(getReport(errorObj,'extended','hyperlinks','off'),'SAM_
Machine v1.0');
end

function current_line_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject    handle to current_line (see GCBO)
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
% handles    structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)

% Hints: get(hObject,'String') returns contents of current_line
as text
%         str2double(get(hObject,'String')) returns contents of
current_line as a double

% --- Executes during object creation, after setting all
properties.
function current_line_CreateFcn(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject    handle to current_line (see GCBO)
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB

```

```
% handles      empty - handles not created until after all
CreateFcns called
```

```
% Hint: edit controls usually have a white background on
Windows.
```

```
%      See ISPC and COMPUTER.
```

```
if      ispc      &&      isequal(get(hObject,'BackgroundColor'),
get(0,'defaultUicontrolBackgroundColor'))
    set(hObject,'BackgroundColor','white');
end
```

```
function serial_port_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
```

```
% hObject      handle to serial_port (see GCBO)
```

```
% eventdata      reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
```

```
% handles      structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)
```

```
% Hints: get(hObject,'String') returns contents of serial_port
as text
```

```
%      str2double(get(hObject,'String')) returns contents of
serial_port as a double
```

```
% --- Executes during object creation, after setting all
properties.
```

```
function serial_port_CreateFcn(hObject, eventdata, handles)
```

```
% hObject      handle to serial_port (see GCBO)
```

```
% eventdata      reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
```

```
% handles      empty - handles not created until after all
CreateFcns called
```

```
% Hint: edit controls usually have a white background on
Windows.
```

```
%      See ISPC and COMPUTER.
```

```
if      ispc      &&      isequal(get(hObject,'BackgroundColor'),
get(0,'defaultUicontrolBackgroundColor'))
    set(hObject,'BackgroundColor','white');
end
```

```
function G_CodeMini_Path_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
```

```
% hObject      handle to G_CodeMini_Path (see GCBO)
```

```

% eventdata reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
% handles structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)

% Hints: get(hObject,'String') returns contents of
G_CodeMini_Path as text
% str2double(get(hObject,'String')) returns contents of
G_CodeMini_Path as a double

% --- Executes during object creation, after setting all
properties.
function G_CodeMini_Path_CreateFcn(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject handle to G_CodeMini_Path (see GCBO)
% eventdata reserved - to be defined in a future version of
MATLAB
% handles empty - handles not created until after all
CreateFcns called

% Hint: edit controls usually have a white background on
Windows.
% See ISPC and COMPUTER.
if ispc && isequal(get(hObject,'BackgroundColor'),
get(0,'defaultUicontrolBackgroundColor'))
    set(hObject,'BackgroundColor','white');
end

```


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APPENDIX 4: SAM MACHINE MICROCONTROLLER PROGRAM

```
/*
DESIGN: SAM_Machine v1.0 G-CodeMini
AUTHOR: 1. Dennis Mutuma
        2. Samuel Macharia (SirmaxforD)

SAM v1.0 Operates in two Modes: 1. Normal Mode; Mode Switch Closed [0].
                                2. Fix Mode; Mode Switch Open [1].
In Normal Mode, the machine does work as a result of program instruction (G-CodeMini) received from a serial port.
G-CodeMini is a message in the format: X12 Y345 Z678 or X-12 Y-345 Z-678 and executes in the event of a newline.
All operations are in G91 and G00 by default.
In Fix Mode, the machine does work as a result of sb pressing XY Z control knobs.
Fix Mode helps in correcting (fixing) the axes.
It can also be used to forge moves 'manually', set stepper speed (alter G00) or even be used to set home.

<Muchas gracias>
<Divertirse>

Rev: http://engineeringmechatronics.wordpress.com
*/

#include <Stepper.h>
#include <LiquidCrystal.h>

//Then motor steps
//Change this to fit the number of steps per revolution
//for your motor
#define STEPS 16

#define X_EN_AB 2
#define Y_EN_AB 3
#define Z_EN_AB 4

#define X_IN1 22
#define X_IN2 23
#define X_IN3 24
#define X_IN4 25

#define Y_IN1 26
```

```

#define Y_IN2 27
#define Y_IN3 28
#define Y_IN4 29

#define Z_IN1 30
#define Z_IN2 31
#define Z_IN3 32
#define Z_IN4 33

#define X_CW 34
#define X_CCW 35
#define Y_CW 36
#define Y_CCW 37
#define Z_CW 38
#define Z_CCW 39

int X=0;
int Y=0;
int Z=0;
int sign = 1;
const int Fix_Mode=5;
const int speaker_pin=9;

int numTones = 10;
int tones[] = {261, 277, 294, 311, 330, 349, 370, 392, 415,
440};
//          mid C  C#  D    D#  E    F    F#  G    G#  A

// initialize the stepper library:
Stepper x_stepper(STEPS, X_IN1, X_IN2, X_IN3, X_IN4);
Stepper y_stepper(STEPS, Y_IN1, Y_IN2, Y_IN3, Y_IN4);
Stepper z_stepper(STEPS, Z_IN1, Z_IN2, Z_IN3, Z_IN4);

LiquidCrystal lcd(40,41,42,43,44,45);
void setup()
{
    for (int i = 0; i < numTones; i++)
    {
        tone(speaker_pin, tones[i]);
        delay(500);
    }
    noTone(speaker_pin);

    lcd.begin(16,2);

```

```

lcd.print("<SAM_MACHINE!> ");

pinMode(Fix_Mode, INPUT);
digitalWrite(Fix_Mode, HIGH);

pinMode(X_CW, INPUT);
pinMode(X_CCW, INPUT);
pinMode(Y_CW, INPUT);
pinMode(Y_CCW, INPUT);
pinMode(Z_CW, INPUT);
pinMode(Z_CCW, INPUT);

// set the speed at say, 60 rpm:
x_stepper.setSpeed(160);
y_stepper.setSpeed(160);
z_stepper.setSpeed(160);
// initialize the serial port:
Serial.begin(9600);
delay(2500); //Let the arduino settle before communication
(with matlab).
Serial.setTimeout(50);

}
void loop()
{
  lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
  lcd.print(millis()/1000);
  int val_Fix_Mode=digitalRead(Fix_Mode);

if (val_Fix_Mode==LOW) //Normal Mode
{
  Serial.println(" NORMAL MODE! ");
  lcd.print("NORMAL MODE!");
  Serial.println(" WAITING FOR G-CodeMini ");

if( Serial.available())
{
  digitalWrite(X_EN_AB, HIGH);
  digitalWrite(Y_EN_AB, HIGH);
  digitalWrite(Z_EN_AB, HIGH);

char ch = Serial.read();
  Serial.println(" I've RECEIVED Digits. Wait as I work on em
");

  X=Serial.parseInt();
  if( ch == '-')

```

```

    {
        sign = -1;
        X = X * sign ;// set value to the accumulated value
    }

Y=Serial.parseInt();
if( ch == '-')
{
    sign = -1;
    Y = Y * sign ;// set value to the accumulated value
}

Z=Serial.parseInt();
if( ch == '-')
{
    sign = -1;
    Z = Z * sign ;// set value to the accumulated value
}
Serial.println(X);
Serial.println(Y);
Serial.println(Z);

//else if( ch == '10')
//{
x_stepper.step(X);
y_stepper.step(Y);
z_stepper.step(Z);
//}

X = 0; // reset value to 0 ready for the next sequence of
digits
Y = 0;
Z = 0;
sign = 1;

digitalWrite(X_EN_AB,LOW);
digitalWrite(Y_EN_AB,LOW);
digitalWrite(Z_EN_AB,LOW);
//lcd.print("IDLE!");
}

}

if(val_Fix_Mode==HIGH) //Fix Mode
{
    Serial.println(" FIX MODE! ");
}

```

```

Serial.println(" Move Steppers Yourself as you Check My LCD
");
lcd.print("FIX MODE!");
int Speed=analogRead(A1);
int RPM=map(Speed,0,1023,0,100);

int x_fwd=digitalRead(X_CW);
int x_rvs=digitalRead(X_CCW);
int y_fwd=digitalRead(Y_CW);
int y_rvs=digitalRead(Y_CCW);
int z_fwd=digitalRead(Z_CW);
int z_rvs=digitalRead(Z_CCW);

if(x_fwd==1 && x_rvs==0 && RPM>5)
{
  lcd.print("X-");
  digitalWrite(X_EN_AB,HIGH);
  x_stepper.setSpeed(RPM);
  x_stepper.step(1);
  digitalWrite(X_EN_AB,LOW);
  //tone(speaker_pin,freq,duration);
}

if(x_rvs==1 && x_fwd==0 && RPM>5)
{
  lcd.print("X+");
  digitalWrite(X_EN_AB,HIGH);
  x_stepper.setSpeed(RPM);
  x_stepper.step(-1);
  digitalWrite(X_EN_AB,LOW);
  //tone(speaker_pin,freq,duration);
}

if(y_fwd==1 && y_rvs==0 && RPM>5)
{
  lcd.print("Y-");
  digitalWrite(Y_EN_AB,HIGH);
  y_stepper.setSpeed(RPM);
  y_stepper.step(1);
  digitalWrite(Y_EN_AB,LOW);
  //tone(speaker_pin,freq,duration);
}

if(y_rvs==1 && y_fwd==0 && RPM>5)
{
  lcd.print("Y+");
  digitalWrite(Y_EN_AB,HIGH);
}

```

```

    y_stepper.setSpeed(RPM);
    y_stepper.step(-1);
    digitalWrite(Y_EN_AB, LOW);
    //tone(speaker_pin, freq, duration);
}

if(z_fwd==1 && z_rvs==0 && RPM>5)
{
    lcd.print("Z-");
    digitalWrite(Z_EN_AB, HIGH);
    z_stepper.setSpeed(RPM);
    z_stepper.step(1);
    digitalWrite(Z_EN_AB, LOW);
    //tone(speaker_pin, freq, duration);
}

    if(z_rvs==1 && z_fwd==0 && RPM>5)
{
    lcd.print("Z+");
    digitalWrite(Z_EN_AB, HIGH);
    z_stepper.setSpeed(RPM);
    z_stepper.step(-1);
    digitalWrite(Z_EN_AB, LOW);
    //tone(speaker_pin, freq, duration);
}

else
{
    digitalWrite(X_EN_AB, LOW);
    digitalWrite(Y_EN_AB, LOW);
    digitalWrite(Z_EN_AB, LOW);
    //lcd.print("IDLE!");
}
}
}
/*
Reference:
http://www.arduino.cc/en/Reference/Stepper
*/

```